

EFFECTS OF ACTIVITY-BASED TEACHING ON THE ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF STUDENTS IN BIOLOGY IN SELECTED SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ILORIN, KWARA STATE.

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Abstract

The study examined the effects of activity-based teaching methods on students' academic performance in Biology. The study sample consists of 100 senior secondary school II (SSS II) students from the two purposively selected private secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis. The two schools were selected based on gender and availability of equipments. An instrument, Biology Performance Test (BPT) was constructed based on some aspects of Biology topic (Organization of Life in Organisms) and validated by experts. The reliability co-efficient was done using test-retest method at reliability value of 0.66. The research was a quasi-experimental type with pretest and post-test administered to each of the two groups i.e. control group and experimental group. T-test was employed to analyze the test results of the two groups at 0.05 level of significance. Two hypotheses were formulated, the first hypothesis was rejected, because there was significant difference between the performance of students taught with activity-based method and the second hypothesis based on gender (male and female) was accepted because gender had no effect on the performance of students taught using activity-based method.

Key words: Activity-based teaching, students' performance, Biology

Introduction

Biology is one of the science subjects taught in senior secondary schools in Nigeria. According to the West African Examination Council (WAEC), SSCE result of the school sampled, students' performance in Biology subject at the Senior School Certificate Examination had remained persistently poor. Several reasons had been suggested for this poor performance of students among which is the poor teaching methods adopted by most biology teachers and the failure by most teachers to teach the practical aspect of biology. In biology teaching, the importance of integrating practical (activity) work with theory cannot be over-emphasized. The integration of activity work with theory makes the learners not to be passive and this could create a fun filled and an enjoyable scene in the class, which in turn could make the learners to easily grasp the lesson been taught. Akale & Usman (1993) also observed that practical activities enhance better learning and understanding of science.

For effective science teaching and learning, varieties or series of practical work strategy are highlighted by Bajah (1984). These are whole class activity in groups, individual student activity, group project work in out-of-school special activity, individual project work and teacher's demonstrations. Dyasi (2006) asserts that the teaching process must provide students with the opportunity to make first-hand decisions: what science tools to use for various tasks, how to organize data, how to portray the patterns created by data and what conclusion to accept or reject. Activity-based instruction is a form of instruction/teaching that opposes teacher monopolized teaching/instruction which thrived in antiquity leaving the students as mere recipients and absorbers of knowledge. Its approach is more of providing opportunities for pupils to express their freedom to explore possible ways to solve a certain problem or to manipulate materials with the teacher's role reduced to that of a facilitator. (Ryan, 2010). Activity-based

- Students learn at their own pace.
- Provision of more time for self-directed learning and teacher-directed learning is reduced considerably.
- Group learning, mutual learning and self learning are promoted.
- Teachers' teaching is judiciously distributed among students.
- Students' participation in every step is ensured in the process of learning.
- Evaluation is in-built in the system.
- Rote learning is discouraged and almost no scope for rote learning.
- Freedom to students' learning as he/she choose his activity.

Biology is an activity oriented subject which focuses more on knowledge applications than mere knowledge acquisition. Hence, activity based method of teaching should be integrated with theory lessons thus, making it more memorable.

Activity-based method of teaching is a teaching technique that combines practical work with theory, but lay more emphasis on 'doing' with the learner. The learners are the active participants while the teacher guides with instruction and explanation where necessary. This study determined the effectiveness of activity-based approach to the teaching of Biology instead of relying on lecture method alone where students are passive learners.

Statement of the Problem

The level of failure in the sciences at the Senior Secondary School Examination (SSCE) is increasing at an alarming rate. For an instance the WAEC Chief Examiner's report (2008) shows that the performance of candidates in Biology in 2008 was poorer than the performance in 2007. Given the above scenario, this study focused on effects of activity-based teaching on the performances of students in biology.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the effect of activity-based teaching method on the performance of students in Biology in Ilorin, Kwara state, Nigeria.

Specifically, the study determined:

- (a) the performance of students taught with activity-based approach and those taught with conventional method;
- (b) influence of gender on the performance of the students.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested in the study,

H01: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of students taught using activity-based method and those taught using the conventional method.

H02: There is no significant difference in the performance of male and female students taught using activity-based method.

Methodology

Research type

The study adopted a pretest-post-test experimental design involving two groups: the experimental and control groups. The experimental group was exposed to a treatment while the control group was not exposed to the treatment.

Sample

The sample for this study consists of 100 SSS II students from two selected secondary schools in Ilorin metropolis, Kwara state.

Instrument

The research instrument used was Biology Performance Test (BPT) based on Biology topic, the organization of life in organism. The items were drawn using WAEC and NECO (SSCE) past examination questions. It was re-structured after considering experts' constructive criticisms. The reliability was done using test-retest method and correlation index of 0.66 was obtained.

Data Analysis Technique

The data gathered from the students in experimental group and control group was analyzed using the t-test to determine the effect of the treatment.

Results & Discussion

The results are presented in accordance with the hypotheses.

Hypothesis1: There is no significant difference between the academic performance of students taught in the experimental group and those in the control group.

Table1: t-test showing the difference in the academic performance of experimental and control group.

Group	N	ΣX	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	tcal	t-table
Experimental	50	1674	33.48	6.9007	98	4.649	2.00
Control	50	1391	27.82	5.1478			

From Table 1, it was observed that the result of the analysis is significant. Therefore, the performance of students taught using activity-based method are better than those taught using conventional method.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the academic performance of male and female participants in the experimental and control groups.

Table 2: t-test table showing the difference in the academic performance between male and female in the experimental group.

Variable	N	ΣX	$\bar{X}$	SD	df	tcal	t-table
Male	26	887	34.12	5.04	48	0.939	2.00
Female	24	786	32.75	5.24			

Table 2 revealed that gender had no effect on the performance of students in the experimental group.

Summary of Major Findings.

- Participants taught using activity-based method performed better than those taught using conventional method.
- Both male and female participants in experimental group performed well in this study. Therefore, the study is not gender biased.

Recommendations

- Teachers should adopt activity-based method of teaching where students are active participants and not passive learners.
- There should be a monitoring/supervising team that monitors the activities of teachers when in class.
- Government should be implored to provide necessary equipment and appropriate teaching aids that would facilitate exploratory teaching in science and biology in particular.

Practice, through manipulation and free self-expression is the benefit that students get from activity-based teaching/instructions, and this makes learning permanent in a more meaningful way.

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Abstract

In order to understand the global virus spread a system is either infected or not. If we do not detect the infected system in a timely manner, the infection will spread to other systems. This paper discusses the advantages and disadvantages of activity-based teaching. The main aim of this work is to examine various ways of controlling or copying viral codes. Also is to study why people write viral codes and give the economic consequences of viruses to organizations, so that they will be guided to controlling the spread of viruses. The work will be a useful guide to University researchers and research institutions in the creation and control of viruses so that policy makers can enact laws for the management and control of viruses.

Keywords: Managing, Viral attack, Computer systems.

Introduction

Computer Viruses

A computer virus is a self replicating piece of computer code (instructions) that can partially or fully attach itself to files or applications and cause the computer to do what it was not originally intended to do (John and

REFERENCES

Akale, M. A. & Usman, I. (1993). Effect of practical activities on achievement in Integrated Science among Junior Secondary School Students in Kaduna State. *Journal of the Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria*. 28(182):102-108.

Bajah, S.T. (1984). Continuous Assessment and Practical work in Science Teaching: A plea for pragmatism. *Journal of the Science Teachers' Association of Nigeria*. 22(2):43-48.

Dyasi, H. (2006). What Children Gain by learning through Inquiry. *Foundations V.2*. Retrieved on 2-12-2012 from <http://www.exploratorium.edu>.

Ryan Subong (2010). Advantages and disadvantages of activity-based instruction. Retrieved from www.helium.com on Dec.2nd 2012 West African Examination Council (WAEC), (2006) Chief Examiner's Report, Lagos.

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